

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D8.1 Report on the market analysis and benchmarking with competing technologies

Date of delivery 13/10/2022

Authors FISE: Nicholas Chandler, Shahab Rohani,
Thomas Fluri

KAE: Simon Schütrumpf, Andreas Pöppinghaus

Institution Fraunhofer ISE, KAEFER

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764048.

Document tracks

Identification		POLYPHEM_D8.1_Market analysis & Benchmark
TITLE OF DELIVERABLE	Report on the market analysis and benchmarking with competing technologies	
Author(s)	Nicholas Chandler, Simon Schütrumpf, Shahab Rohani, Thomas Fluri, Andreas Pöppinghaus	
Reviewers(s)	Alain Ferriere	
Related Work Package (s)	WP8: Assessment of the Deployment of the Technology Developed in the Project	
Beneficiary responsible of delivery	Fraunhofer ISE	
Due date of delivery	31/05/2022	
Actual date of submission/revision	13/10/2022	
Number of pages	22	
SUMMARY	<p><i>This document is the deliverable D8.1 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 8 (Assessment of the Deployment of the Technology Developed in the Project). In this WP, a strategy is developed for the commercial deployment of POLYPHEM. This deliverable contains the information for Task 8.1. This task focuses on benchmarking study where techno-economic performance of POLYPHEM is evaluated against three competing technologies in two different locations with favourable conditions for POLYPHEM.</i></p>	
Dissemination level	Public (PU)	
Repository	https://dms.polyphem-project.eu	

Document History and Validation

Date	Name	Comments
01/02/2022	Nicholas Chandler	Creation
24/08/2022	Thomas Fluri	Review 1
02/09/2022	Alain Ferriere	Review 2
05/09/2022	Shahab Rohani	Final

All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
Acronym	POLYPHEM
Call identifier	H2020 LCE-07-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement N°	764048
Starting Date	01/04/2018
Duration	48 months
Website	https://www.polyphem-project.eu
Keywords	Renewable electricity; Energy collection, conversion and storage; Renewable energy
Additional keywords	Concentrated solar power; Solar tower system; Combined cycle; Gas-turbine; Thermal energy storage; Organic Rankine cycle; Process control
Beneficiaries	CNRS, CEA, CIEMAT, Arraela S.L., Fraunhofer ISE, Kaefer Isoliertechnik, Orcan Energy, Euronovia, Aalborg CSP

The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764048

Table of content

1. SUMMARY	6
2. CASE STUDY METHODOLOGY	6
2.1 POLYPHEM Project	6
2.2 TECHNO-ECONOMIC BENCHMARKING	7
2.3 DEFINITION OF TECHNOLOGIES	8
2.4 CRITERIA FOR SITE SELECTION AND DEPLOYMENT	12
3. CASE STUDY A: ANTOFAGASTA, CHILE	13
3.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION (WIKIPEDIA.COM 2022A)	13
3.2 EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGIES	14
4. CASE STUDY B: KEETMANSHOOP, NAMIBIA	16
4.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION (WIKIPEDIA.COM 2022B; ENCYCLOPEDIA BRITANNICA 2018)	16
4.2 EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGIES	16
5. BENCHMARK RESULTS & DISCUSSION	19
6. CONCLUSION	21
7. PUBLICATION BIBLIOGRAPHY	22

List of Figures

Figure 1: Summer POLYPHEM Power Delivery Profile in Antofagasta, Chile [Nov. 9 – 11]	6
Figure 2: Effect of Real Interest Rates on the POLYPHEM LCOE Price	8
Figure 3: Summer PV+BESS Generation Profile in Antofagasta, Chile	9
Figure 4: PV+BESS Pricing Sensitivity with a 7.5% Interest Rate	10
Figure 5: LCOE Sensitivity - Diesel Pricing and Real Interest Rate	11
Figure 6: LCOE Sensitivity – Grid Extension with a grid power price of 15 c\$/kWh	12
Figure 7: Direct Normal Radiation Map of Chile (Solargis 2020)	13
Figure 8: Chile – POLYPHEM	14
Figure 9: Chile – PV+BESS Monthly Generation Profile	14
Figure 10: Chile – POLYPHEM Cost Sensitivity Analysis	14
Figure 11: Chile – PV+BESS Cost Sensitivity Analysis	14
Figure 12: Chile – Diesel Generator Cost Sensitivity Analysis	15
Figure 13: Chile – Grid Extension Cost Sensitivity Analysis	15
Figure 14: Direct Normal Radiation Map of Namibia (Solargis 2020)	16
Figure 15: Namibia – POLYPHEM Monthly Generation Profile	17
Figure 16: Namibia – PV+BESS	17
Figure 17: Namibia – POLYPHEM Cost Sensitivity Analysis	17
Figure 18: Namibia – PV+BESS Cost Sensitivity Analysis	17
Figure 19: Namibia – Diesel Generator Cost Sensitivity Analysis	18
Figure 20: Namibia – Grid Extension Cost Sensitivity Analysis	18

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of cost based on production cost of POLYPHEM project	7
Table 2: Real Interest Rates Assumed per Country	7
Table 3: PV Installation Costs (International Renewable Energy Agency 2021)	9
Table 4: BESS Installation Costs (International Renewable Energy Agency 2017)	10
Table 5: Cost of Diesel per Country (2016) (TheGlobalEconomy.com 2022)	10
Table 6: Cost of Electricity per Country (2021) (globalpetrolprices.com 2021)	11
Table 7: Overview of Potential Deployment Locations (Solargis 2020)	12
Table 8: Summary of Technology Performance in the Antofagasta region, Chile	15
Table 9: Summary of Technology Performance in the Keetmanshoop region, Namibia	18
Table 10: Summary of Techno-Economic Results for Both Locations	20
Table 11: Techno-Economic Comparison of POLYPHEM vs. Competing Technologies	21

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure (Initial Installation Cost)
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential: only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiation
KAE	Kaefer Isoliertechnik GmbH
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
M	Month
MS	Milestone
OPEX	Operation Expenditure (Operational Costs)
ORC	‘Orcan Energy AG’ or ‘Organic Rankine Cycle’
PU	Public
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package
μGT	Micro Gas Turbine

1. SUMMARY

To determine the most effective roadmap to bring the POLYPHEM project to market, a technical and financial benchmarking study with competing technologies to provide electric generation for various locations was conducted. **Section 2** describes the case study methodology, information regarding the competing technologies and the deployment sites. **Section 3** and **Section 4** are case studies which catalogue and analyse the performance per technology deployed in the respective location. Then in **Section 5**, the different case study results are catalogued and evaluated against each other. Lastly, **Section 6** concludes this study.

2. CASE STUDY METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the POLYPHEM project is to improve a small-scale solar power tower plant design for remote areas with needs such as electric generation, industrial heat production or desalination. With the POLYPHEM concept studied and verified in the previous deliverable reports, the next step is to identify locations where POLYPHEM can be successfully deployed. Additionally, in each location competing technologies are also considered to benchmark the techno-economic effectiveness of POLYPHEM.

2.1 POLYPHEM PROJECT

The POLYPHEM concept consists of a 40-meter-high solar receiver tower, heliostats, solarized micro gas-turbine, a Rankine organic cycle machine, and an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The overall footprint of the plant depends on the annual DNI of the location and the resulting optimized solar field aperture area. Practically, the POLYPHEM concept is ideal for industry purposes with high heat requirements or converting this to electric generation in rural areas.

Techno-Economic Assumptions

As previously demonstrated, the POLYPHEM plant can operate under several different operating strategies: it can either follow a demand curve or it can operate at maximum capacity while simultaneously charging the storage. The latter operating strategy will be considered for this report to evaluate POLYPHEM's full generation potential. As seen in **Figure 1**, the micro gas turbine (μ GT) operates at full load while the stratified storage is being charged. As an increasing amount of excess heat cannot be stored, this is instead delivered to the ORC. This could be due to a slowly reduced temperature difference between bottom and top of the tank as it is being charged. The power generation from the daytime ramp-up of the ORC is then compounded with the μ GT generation. As soon as the storage is fully charged, the ORC operates at full capacity and POLYPHEM can deliver more than 80kW of electricity.

Figure 1: Summer POLYPHEM Power Delivery Profile in Antofagasta, Chile [Nov. 9 – 11]

According to previous studies (Ferrerres 2021), the lifetime is taken as 30 years and the operational costs (OPEX) were taken as 2% of initial installation cost (CAPEX). The production cost figures, shown in **Table 1**, were determined in **Deliverable D8.2** and are assumed to be the benchmark investment cost. The production costs were converted from Euro to U.S. Dollar with an assumed conversion rate of 1.00€ = 1.10\$ in order to compare against the other competing technologies references.

Table 1: Overview of cost based on production cost of POLYPHEM project

Component	Production Cost [€]	Production Cost [\$]	Size - Capacity
Solar Field	87.3 €/m ²	96 \$/m ²	1920-2100 m ²
Solar Receiver	454 €/kW _{th}	499.4 \$/kW _{th}	534.6 kW _{th}
Solar Tower	625 €/m	687.5 \$/m	40 m
Solarized micro Gas Turbine	1530 €/kW _{el}	1683 \$/kW _{el}	76.5 kW _{el}
Heat exchanger	317.5 €/m ²	349.25 \$/m ²	126 m ²
Organic Rankine Cycle	1800 €/kW _{el}	1980 \$/kW _{el}	22 kW _{el}
Thermal Energy Storage	37.5 €/kWh	41.25 \$/kWh	1600 kWh
Plant Controls	50 000 €	55 000 \$	-
Balance of Plant	34 000 €	37 400\$	-
Contingencies	10% of Hybrid Solar Cycle (Top & Bottom)		

2.2 TECHNO-ECONOMIC BENCHMARKING

In **Deliverable D7.4**, a techno-economic optimization for POLYPHEM was performed for several locations. This optimization determined which POLYPHEM configuration would generate the greatest amount of electricity at the lowest cost. This primary benchmarking indicator is referred to as the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), which is the electricity selling price per unit of generated electricity that would be required to recover the costs of investment and operation of the power plant over its lifetime.

As described in the following equation (Christoph Kost et al. 2021), the LCOE is calculated by the sum of the costs divided by the discounted energy production of the power plant over the lifetime:

$$LCOE = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t + F_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_{t,el}}{(1+i)^t}}$$

where I_0 corresponds to the initial capital expenditure, A_t refers to the annual operational costs, F_t refers to the annual fuel or electricity purchased in year t , $M_{t,el}$ is the electricity generated (kWh) by the plant in year t , i is the interest rate, t is the operational year, and n is the lifetime of the plant in years.

Table 2: Real Interest Rates Assumed per Country

Location	Interest Rate
Chile	2.5%
Namibia	7.5%

Since economic scenarios change, different real interest rates (**Table 2**) were considered for each location to further demonstrate pricing sensitivity. As illustrated by the compared interest rates in **Figure 2**, slightly increasing or decreasing the real interest rates can have a significant impact on the system economics. Therefore, when determining potential deployment locations for POLYPHEM, the financial environment of the location must be carefully considered. Additionally, it is assumed that these real interest rates include inflation which consequentially impact the cost of fuel and electricity.

Figure 2: Effect of Real Interest Rates on the POLYPHEM LCOE Price

To compare the effectiveness of each technology in each location, several assumptions were taken. The optimized annual POLYPHEM generation from each location is assumed to be the generation requirement for each technology per location. Furthermore, the maximum electric capacity of POLYPHEM was considered as the target capacity for the other technologies as well.

The methodology to calculate the installation cost, annual maintenance cost, and additional fuel costs per technology are detailed further in their respective section below. Additionally, other factors such as social acceptance and environmental impact per technology were also considered. For each location, local cost assumptions per technology were assumed based upon available literature.

2.3 DEFINITION OF TECHNOLOGIES

For this benchmarking study, POLYPHEM is aimed at providing electricity in isolated environments. Hence, the two common solutions for electricity production in microgrids, solar photovoltaics (PV) with a battery energy storage system (BESS) and diesel generators, have been considered. Additionally, a grid expansion was also considered. Following sections provide detailed analysis of the comparison and describe the methodology to calculate the electricity price of each solution. Note that the study compares market price of electricity (in case of grid expansion) to cost of electricity generation (in case of PV and POLYPHEM technologies). We assumed in this study, that the owner of the production site (PV or POLYPHEM) is the same as the consumer.

2.3.1 PV + BESS

Photovoltaics with a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) is a popular solution for remote electrification. PV technology itself is very mature, widely utilized, and is one of the most affordable forms of renewable technology. Since PV power production is constrained by sufficient irradiation, the technology is often paired with batteries for off-hour production. Battery system technology has significantly improved in performance and environmental friendliness over the last years, transitioning from lead-acid batteries to lithium-ion storage solutions.

Techno-Economic Assumptions

The generation of the PV+BESS per location was determined using Fraunhofer ISE's inhouse simulation tool ColSim. The PV is assumed to be fixed axis and the installed cost of the PV is assumed to be country dependent (**Table 3**). The PV module used is a PV STP330-24 [330 W_p, monocrystalline panel] and the PV inverter used is the Renergy RS-5000 [240V]. The installed cost assumptions of the PV system in **Table 3** were revised using the unitary method.

Table 3: PV Installation Costs (International Renewable Energy Agency 2021)

Location	1.2 DC-AC Ratio	1.8 DC-AC Ratio
Chile	1047 \$/kW _{AC}	1570.5 \$/kW _{AC}
Namibia*	1148 \$/kW _{AC}	1722 \$/kW _{AC}

*Note: South Africa PV costs were assumed for Namibia.

As seen in **Figure 3**, during the summer months in Chile, a PV+BESS system that has a PV sizing of 132/72 kW_{DC/AC} and 100 kWh of Lithium-Ion battery storage is fully charged and then fully discharges in the evening. The PV-BESS system was sized and optimized per location so that its annual yield and night-time BESS generation is equivalent to the POLYPHEM system.

Figure 3: Summer PV+BESS Generation Profile in Antofagasta, Chile

Two types of commonly found batteries were considered: a lead-acid (flooded) battery and a lithium-ion (LFP) battery. The lead acid battery has a lifetime of 9 years and costs approximately 147 \$/kWh while the lithium-ion battery has a lifetime of 13 years and costs approximately 578 \$/kWh (International Renewable Energy Agency 2017). Even though the lead-acid battery is significantly cheaper, the depth of discharge and energy density of the lead-acid battery are lower than the lithium-ion battery. Both batteries were considered to show their cost-sensitivity. The PV maintenance costs are assumed to be 42 \$/kW_{AC}/Year

installed and 1955 \$/System/Year (Odou et al. 2020). While battery replacement was considered, degradation of the battery was not.

Table 4: BESS Installation Costs (International Renewable Energy Agency 2017)

Battery Type	Cost Assumption	Lifetime
Lead-Acid (Flooded)	147 \$/kWh	9 yrs.
Lithium-Ion (LFP)	578 \$/kWh	13 yrs.

In **Figure 4**, the LCOE sensitivity of the two PV+BESS configurations are compared by varying the PV installation costs and the BESS installation costs with an equivalent interest rate of 7.5%. The two figures illustrate that even though the Lithium-Ion BESS system is more expensive, its longer lifetime, infrequency to be replaced and higher efficiency can be more cost effective.

Figure 4: PV+BESS Pricing Sensitivity with a 7.5% Interest Rate

2.3.2 Diesel Generator

Diesel generators are a very common form of remote electric generation. The main benefit of fossil fuel generators is the ability to have constant power generation independent of the weather conditions. However, the system is entirely reliant on fossil fuels, which introduce many other problems. Diesel needs to be delivered regularly, its price fluctuates, and repairs can become very expensive. Most importantly, the environmental impact from diesel generators needs to be considered where large quantities of diesel are required for annual operation. Another critical factor is that in many countries fossil fuel generation is gradually being phased out, so a diesel generator should not be assumed as a long-term viable solution.

Table 5: Cost of Diesel per Country (2016) (TheGlobalEconomy.com 2022)

Location	Diesel Price
Chile	0.65 \$/l
Namibia	0.74 \$/l

Techno-Economic Assumptions

The Generac 80 kW Diesel Generator is assumed to consume 23.8 liters per hour. The generator is assumed to cost 563 \$/kW, have an operation cost of 2000 \$/annual, and have a lifetime of 15 000 operational hours (Odou et al. 2020). It is assumed that 1 liter of diesel emits 2.62 kg/CO₂ (Kawamoto et al. 2019) and that the cost of diesel varies by country (ref. **Table 5**).

As seen in **Figure 5**, the combination of real interest rate and the initial cost of diesel has a great impact on the LCOE, easiestly seen by the the competitive LCOE price of 25 c\$/kWh (yellow line). If no real interest rate is assumed, then the price of diesel can be as high as 60 c\$ per liter of diesel to achieve 25 c\$/kWh, while a 10% real interest rate would require the diesel price to fall 87.5% to achieve the same LCOE. Additionally, only the real interest rate is considered for the LCOE while more complex diesel price behaviors such as diesel price flunctuations or inflation are not considered.

Figure 5: LCOE Sensitivity - Diesel Pricing and Real Interest Rate

2.3.3 Grid Extension

One “simple” solution to bring electricity to an un-electrified region is to connect it to the main grid. While this approach is feasible, it is not always practical. Often, the costs outweigh the benefits to connect areas that are remote and sparsely populated. Additionally, the terrain (mountains, ocean, etc.) can make it very difficult or expensive to connect certain areas. Lastly, the main grid in many countries can be unreliable and is powered by traditional fossil fuels, so in some circumstances an extension would only cause further exasperation on the grid and increase pollution.

Table 6: Cost of Electricity per Country (2021) (globalpetrolprices.com 2021)

Location	Electricity Price
Chile	16.1 c\$/kWh
Namibia	12.3 c\$/kWh

Techno-Economic Assumptions

The cost to extend the grid is assumed to be 15 500 \$/km, maintenance cost is 310 \$/year/kilometer, and that the lifetime of the system is 50 years (Odou et al. 2020). For the location in Chile and Namibia, the site for installment is considered to be located 30 km away from the power grid (Mainali and Dhital 2015). The cost of electricity per country can be found in **Table 6**.

In **Figure 6**, the extension cost and the extension distance are important factors when determining rural electrification. As previously seen, the economic impact of the real interest rate is a decisive factor. If the assumed grid extension cost of 15 500 \$/km is assumed with fixed grid power price of 15 c\$/kWh, the 5% difference in real interest rate reduces the distance for a 25 c\$/kWh by nearly 55%, or from 35 kilometers to 20 kilometers. It continues to play a critical role but when inflation is considered and the annual price of electricity increases year by year, the lifetime cost of electricity increases approximately 50-60%.

Figure 6: LCOE Sensitivity – Grid Extension with a grid power price of 15 c\$/kWh

2.4 CRITERIA FOR SITE SELECTION AND DEPLOYMENT

Considering the requirements for POLYPHEM to be effective and successful, potential deployment locations must meet baseline requirements. The first requirement is that a location needs to have a number of sufficiently sunny days with a high value of direct normal irradiation (DNI). The second key requirement is that the location can fully utilize the POLYPHEM technology, or in other words, be a remote area that does not have an existing grid connection. Lastly, the location should have a high acceptance of renewable technology and could potentially subsidize some POLYPHEM costs.

With these requirements, two potential locations have been considered for evaluation and are briefly described in **Table 7**: the regions surrounding Antofagasta in Chile and Keetmanshoop in Namibia. Each location represents a unique deployment opportunity for the POLYPHEM project. Antofagasta is a fast-growing Chilean mining city near the Atacama Desert with a very high annual DNI. Keetmanshoop is a small, rural town within Namibia. In the sections below, a short case study evaluates the potential for a POLYPHEM plant deployed in these two regions as well as how it performs against the other micro-grid technologies.

Table 7: Overview of Potential Deployment Locations (Solargis 2020)

Comparison Factor	Antofagasta, Chile	Keetmanshoop, Namibia
Population	+350 000	21 000
Latitude [°]	-23.07	-26.57
Altitude [m]	40	1066
Location	Northern Atacama Desert in Chile	Southern Africa near South Africa
Climate	Cold Desert Climate	Cold Desert Climate
Annual GHI [kWh/m ²]	2792	2236
Annual DNI [kWh/m ²]	3829	2500
Accessibility	Port Nearby, Close to Coast	Accessible by multiple highways
Quality of Power Available from Grid	Moderate to High	Insufficient

3. CASE STUDY A: ANTOFAGASTA, CHILE

3.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION (WIKIPEDIA.COM 2022A)

Antofagasta, the capital of the Antofagasta region, is a port city located in the northern part of the Atacama Desert in Chile. The city, with a population of more than 350 000 inhabitants, has been associated with mining but is transitioning into a modern city with other industries and has the highest GDP per capita of Chile. However, the city is slightly isolated from the rest of Chile, being some 1100 km away from the Chilean capital of Santiago.

Not only is the northern region of Chile rich in mineral resources, **Figure 7** shows that the region is rich in solar resources as well. Chile continues to progress towards having 60% of its electricity generated from renewable resources by 2035, with 3104 MW of solar capacity installed, 2801 MW under construction and the new Cerro Dominador 110 MW_{CSP} & 100 MW_{PV} plant about to come online. The transition towards renewable energy in Chile in general fairs well.

Figure 7: Direct Normal Radiation Map of Chile (Solargis 2020)

The Antofagasta region is specifically an interesting option for POLYPHEM since its annual DNI is greater than 3200 kWh/m² and the heat and electrical needs of its mining industry which are located beyond the city center. It is assumed that renewables that can be remotely deployed are both economically and technically appealing since they reduce carbon emissions as well as eliminate fuel transport needs. Since the capital is a modern Chilean city, it is assumed that access to diesel is widely available and that the region itself has a reliable utility grid.

3.2 EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGIES

The optimized POLYPHEM configuration for this location produces an annual electricity yield of 270.6 MWh with an aperture area of 1920 m². To produce the same amount, a 72 kW_{AC} / 132 kW_{DC} of installed PV with a 100-kWh Li-Ion BESS system is required. As seen in **Figure 8** and **Figure 9**, the annual generation profiles of the two technologies and the share of nighttime generation for POLYPHEM and PV+BESS of 27.5 MWh (10.2%) and 27.9 MWh (10.3%) respectively, are very similar.

Figure 8: Chile – POLYPHEM Monthly Generation Profile

Figure 9: Chile – PV+BESS Monthly Generation Profile

When costs are considered, the initial installation cost of POLYPHEM (\$917 561) compared to the PV+BESS system (\$228 676) is 4 times greater and the POLYPHEM lifetime operational expenses are approximately 4.2 times greater. As a result, POLYPHEM’s LCOE of 22.98 c\$/kWh is 3.4 times higher than the calculated LCOE of 6.79 c\$/kWh of the PV+BESS system. As demonstrated in **Figure 10** and **Figure 11**, in order for the two technologies to reach a similar LCOE, the POLYPHEM would be required to cut its installed costs and the BESS price would need to increase.

Figure 10: Chile – POLYPHEM Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 11: Chile – PV+BESS Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 12: Chile – Diesel Generator Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 13: Chile – Grid Extension Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Of the technologies considered, the diesel generator is the most expensive solution due to the high cost and consumption of diesel. As seen in **Figure 12**, only if the real interest rate was maintained at 2.5 % and the average cost of diesel stayed below 30 c\$/liter would the diesel generator be a more affordable than POLYPHEM. Alternatively, only in certain scenarios could a grid expansion could be justified as seen from the sensitivity analysis shown in **Figure 13**. Assuming that the new location is 20 kilometers away and the grid power price is maintained at 16 c\$/kWh, POLYPHEM would be a more attractive solution. If the location were within 22 kilometers with the current power price or if the power price fell below 11.3 c\$/kWh for a 30 kilometer distance, would a grid extension be a favored solution.

Table 8: Summary of Technology Performance in the Antofagasta region, Chile

	POLYPHEM	PV+BESS	Diesel Generator	Grid Expansion
Local Cost of Resource	-	-	0.65 USD/liter	16.1 USD/kWh
Installation Cost	9315 \$/kW	PV: 1570.5 \$/kW _{AC} BESS: 578 \$/kWh	563 \$/kW	15 500 \$/km
Maintenance Cost	2% of CAPEX/Annual	PV: 42 \$/kW/yr. BESS: 1955\$/yr.	2000 \$/yr	310 \$/km/yr.
Replacements	None	PV: None BESS: 1x	7x	None
Initial CAPEX	\$ 917 561	\$ 228 676	\$ 315 280	\$ 465 000
Total OPEX (Technology Life)	\$ 384 097	\$ 91 735	OPEX: \$ 41 861 Fuel: \$ 1 095 225	OPEX: \$ 194 652 kWh \$ 911 862
Total Lifetime Costs	\$ 1 301 658	\$ 320 411	\$ 1 925 683	\$ 1 571 513
1st Year Generation	270 589 kWh	270 270 kWh	270 600 kWh	270 600 kWh
Estimated LCOE	22.98 cUSD/kWh	6.79 cUSD/kWh	34.00 cUSD/kWh	27.75 cUSD/kWh

4. CASE STUDY B: KEETMANSHOOP, NAMIBIA

4.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF LOCATION (WIKIPEDIA.COM 2022B; ENCYCLOPEDIA BRITANNICA 2018)

Keetmanshoop is a small town with a population of about 21 000 inhabitants. It is located in the south-eastern, arid region of Namibia. It is considered the capital of southern Namibia and provides an important traffic junction from the capital of Namibia, Windhoek, 460 km to the north, the port town of Luderitz 350 km to the west, and several South African towns to the east and south. The main industry of the town is based upon goods such as sheepskins, processed foods and leather goods.

Figure 14: Direct Normal Radiation Map of Namibia (Solargis 2020)

The solar irradiation conditions surrounding Keetmanshoop are very favorable for CSP, having an annual DNI value exceeding 2900 kWh/m² and a mean sunshine duration of 3,870 hours per year (Figure 14). While only 31% of rural Namibia has access to electricity (US Agency for International Development 2016), renewables are widely implemented in the country with 163 MW of solar and 347 MW of hydro. The good solar conditions and the wide acceptance of renewable technologies make the rural region surrounding Keetmanshoop another interesting location for a POLYPHEM plant.

4.2 EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGIES

When the different technologies are evaluated, a similar outcome emerges when comparing the results as in the case of the Antofagasta region. The optimized POLYPHEM configuration produces annually an electricity yield with 261.9 MWh with a slightly larger aperture area of 2100 m². To produce an equivalent amount, a 77.5 kW_{AC} / 137.5 kW_{DC} of installed PV with a 275 kWh Lead-Acid BESS system is required. As seen in **Figure 16** and **Figure 15**, the annual generation profiles of the two technologies are very similar and the share of nighttime generation for POLYPHEM and PV+BESS is 25.1 MWh (9.6%) and 26.3 MWh (10.0%), respectively.

Figure 15: Namibia – POLYPHEM Monthly Generation Profile

Figure 16: Namibia – PV+BESS Monthly Generation Profile

When costs are considered, the installation cost of POLYPHEM (\$934 841) is 3.7 times greater compared to the PV+BESS system (\$254 730) and its lifetime operation expenses are approximately 3.8 times greater. As a result, POLYPHEM’s LCOE of 37.37 c\$/kWh is 3.3 times greater than the calculated LCOE of 11.15 c\$/kWh. As further demonstrated in *Figure 17* and *Figure 18*, in order for the LCOE of the two technologies to meet parity, the PV+BESS costs would have to increase and POLYPHEM would be required to reduce its installation costs by approximately a third or increase its annual yield capability. The 60% increase of the Antafagasta LCOE can be attributed to three reasons: a 3 % decrease in annual yield, a 9% increase in solarfield size, but the greatest impact was the increase of real interest rate to 7.5%. A real interest rate of 2.5% would result in an LCOE of 24.2 c\$/kWh, close to the LCOE achieved in Antofagasta.

Figure 17: Namibia – POLYPHEM Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 18: Namibia – PV+BESS Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 19: Namibia – Diesel Generator Cost Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 20: Namibia – Grid Extension Cost Sensitivity Analysis

At 74 c\$/liter, the cost of diesel makes generator the most expensive solution. As seen in **Figure 19**, with real interest rate maintained at 7.5%, the cost of diesel would have to fall below 40 c\$/liter to be competitive with POLYPHEM while it would produce nearly 6126 tons of CO₂ emissions over the 30-year period. Even if there was an unlikely scenario where no real interest rates were assumed, the cost of diesel would have to decrease by 35% to be competitive with POLYPHEM. The cost of grid expansion, however, is competitive with POLYPHEM. Assuming a grid power price is 12.3 c\$/kWh, POLYPHEM would be more economically competitive if the installation was more than 40 kilometers away. In order for POLYPHEM to be competitive at a 30 kilometer distance, the Namibian power price would have to be higher than 18.8c\$/kWh. The competitiveness of the grid extension is due to two main reasons: first the relatively low cost of electricity and, second, the high interest rate of POLYPHEM. If either of these factors were to increase or decrease respectively, POLYPHEM would become the more affordable solution.

Table 9: Summary of Technology Performance in the Keetmanshoop region, Namibia

	POLYPHEM	PV+BESS	Diesel Generator	Grid Expansion
Local Cost of Resource	-	-	0.74 USD/liter	12.3 USD/kWh
Installation Cost	9491 \$/kW	PV: 1722 \$/kW _{AC} BESS: 147 \$/kWh	563 \$/kW	15 500 \$/km
Maintenance Cost	2% of CAPEX/Annual	PV: 42 \$/kW/yr. BESS: 1955 \$/yr.	2000 \$/yr.	310 \$/km/yr.
Replacements	None	PV: None BESS: 3x	7x	None
Initial CAPEX	\$ 934 841	\$ 254 730	\$ 315 280	\$ 465 000
Total OPEX (Technology Life)	\$ 220 817	\$ 58 076	OPEX: \$ 23 621 Fuel: \$ 681 215	OPEX: \$ 109 837 kWh \$ 380 602
Total Lifetime Costs	\$ 1 155 658	\$ 312 806	\$ 2 065 256	\$ 955 438
1 st Year Generation	261 861 kWh	262 436 kWh	262 000 kWh	262 000 kWh
Estimated LCOE	37.37 cUSD/kWh	11.15 cUSD/kWh	66.74 cUSD/kWh	30.88 cUSD/kWh

5. BENCHMARK RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Four different technologies, POLYPHEM, PV+BESS, a diesel generator and grid extension, were evaluated at two remote locations in Chile and Namibia. At both locations, regions either surrounding a desert city in South America and a rural town in Southern Africa, represented unique cases where POLYPHEM could be successfully deployed. Location specific assumptions were considered, such as real interest rates, diesel price, electricity costs, and country specific PV pricing.

For the two locations, the POLYPHEM configuration was optimized for the greatest amount of generation with the specified storage at the lowest price. For the locations in Chile and Namibia, the POLYPHEM plant would be able to generate 270.6 MWh and 261.9 respectively, where 9–10% of this generation is dispatched from the 1.6 MWh of thermal storage at night. The cost targets used for POLYPHEM can be found in **Table 1**.

According to these results, the other three technologies were configured to best be compared with POLYPHEM. The PV systems were optimized to match both the annual generation and the night time generation of POLYPHEM using two different BESS technologies, lead-acid (flooded) and Lithium Ion (LFP). For the diesel generator and the grid expansion, the annual generation requirement for the locations in Chile and Namibia was assumed to be 270 MWh and 262 MWh respectively. The cost assumptions for these different technologies can be found in the aforementioned sections **2.3.1**, **2.3.2**, and **2.3.3**.

From **Table 10**, several observations can be made.

First, this study shows that the POLYPHEM technology is able to deliver electricity at the target cost aimed for this project. For the cost of electricity per technology, the LCOE of POLYPHEM was more expensive than the PV+BESS solution, competitive with grid expansion, and significantly less expensive than the diesel generators. As demonstrated when comparing POLYPHEM to a grid expansion in the two different locations, the real interest rates assumed for the technology had a significant effect. For areas with a high interest rate and low electricity purchase price, as demonstrated with Namibia, the cost-competitiveness of grid expansion should be considered.

Second, the installation cost (CAPEX) of POLYPHEM, is significantly higher than the rest of the technologies. The installed cost for POLYPHEM was two to four times greater than the other technologies considered. The expensive installation costs can be justified when compared against the overall lifetime costs of grid expansion or a diesel generator which include the purchased electricity and fuel. However, these high capital costs further reduce POLYPHEM's financial competitiveness when high interest rates are considered.

Third, is the high pricing disparity between POLYPHEM and PV+BESS where both the installation and lifetime costs of POLYPHEM are significantly higher than a PV+BESS configuration. The low pricing of the PV+BESS technology can be largely attributed to the large economy of scale with increased demand and advancements made in the technology.

These three observations are from specific benchmarking scenario results where POLYPHEM is evaluated for solely electricity generation. In the areas where the performance of POLYPHEM is less than satisfactory, there are multiple aspects where its overall competitiveness can be improved.

First, the configuration of the POLYPHEM system should be re-evaluated. One example is to enlarge the micro gas turbine from 76.5 to 100 kW, an upgrade that would require minimal cost. By doing so, not only will the daytime generation increase, but the overall heat recovery potential, bottom cycle utilization, and thermal storage capacity would also increase.

Second, the POLYPHEM bottom cycle should be repurposed as a combined heat and power cycle, instead of solely on electric generation. While the 4-6 % thermal to electric conversion efficiency of the ORC can be lucrative during nighttime electricity demands, selling or utilizing the heat in other areas such as industrial heat, thermal desalination, or district heating could be more profitable than a PV+BESS alternative.

Last, economic realities are not fixed and can quickly change. This study did not take into account rising inflation, market volatility, and other economic factors that affect all competing technologies. One strong opportunity that POLYPHEM presents is to be a renewable technology independent of rare material that can be completely sourced within the EU. By doing so, further risks such as offshore manufacturing, international supply chain issues, and the increased demand for rare materials can be avoided.

Table 10: Summary of Techno-Economic Results for Both Locations

		Antofagasta, Chile	Keetmanshoop, Namibia
	Assumed Power Price	16.1 c\$/kWh	12.3 c\$/kWh
	Real Interest Rate	2.5%	7.5%
	Diesel Cost	0.65 \$/liter	0.74 \$/liter
	PV Size	132/72 kW _{DC/AC}	137.5/77.5 kW _{DC/AC}
	BESS Size	100 kWh Lithium Ion (LFP)	275 kWh Lead Acid (Flooded)
LCOE (c\$/kWh)	POLYPHEM	22.98	37.37
	PV+BESS	6.79	11.15
	Generator	34.00	66.74
	Grid Ext. (30km)	27.75	30.88
CAPEX (\$)	POLYPHEM	\$ 917 561	\$ 934 841
	PV+BESS	\$ 228 676	\$ 254 730
	Generator	\$ 315 280	\$ 315 280
	Grid Ext. (30km)	\$ 465 000	\$ 465 000
Lifetime Costs	POLYPHEM	\$ 1 301 658	\$ 1 155 658
	PV+BESS	\$ 320 411	\$ 312 806
	Generator	\$ 1 925 683	\$ 2 065 256
	Grid Ext.	\$ 1 571 513	\$ 955 438
First Year Generation (kWh/yr.)	POLYPHEM	270 589	261 861
	PV+BESS	260 800	254 255
	Generator	270 600	262 000
	Grid Ext.	270 600	262 000
	1st Year Diesel Cost	\$ 52 327	\$ 58 989
	Avg. Yearly Emissions	6327 Tons CO ₂	6126 Tons CO ₂

6. CONCLUSION

The POLYPHEM concept was evaluated against three competing technologies, PV+BESS, a diesel generator and grid extension, in two locations, the regions surrounding Antofagasta, Chile and Keetmanshoop, Namibia. For each location, a POLYPHEM plant with 1.6 MWh of storage was optimized for the highest amount of generation at the lowest cost. The competing technologies were then configured so that they could be fairly compared against POLYPHEM. Overall POLYPHEM was found to be more expensive than the PV+BESS solution, competitive with grid expansion, and significantly less expensive than diesel generators.

It must be noted that POLYPHEM is not comparable with large multi-MW CSP plants, which have much higher capacity factors and much lower LCOEs.

Table 11: Techno-Economic Comparison of POLYPHEM vs. Competing Technologies

Comparison Factor	POLYPHEM	PV+BESS	Diesel Generator	Grid Expansion
Investment Cost	9300 – 9500 \$/kW	3150 – 3300 \$/kW	563 \$/kW	4700 \$/kW
Replacement Frequency Over Operation Life	None	PV: None BESS: 2-3	7	None
First Year Costs	30 000 – 35 000 \$/yr	11 600 – 14 000 \$/yr	53 000 – 55 000 \$/yr	38 000 – 52 000 \$/yr
Generation Dependency	Solar Irradiation	Solar Irradiation	Fossil Fuel	Pre-Existing Infrastructure
Sensitive to Fuel/Market Pricing	No	No	Very	Very
Estimated LCOE	23 – 38 c\$/kWh	6.5 – 11 c\$/kWh	34 – 66 c\$/kWh	25 – 33 c\$/kWh
Lifetime	30 Years	PV: 25 Years Bess: 9 - 13 Years	15 000 hours	30 Years
Carbon Emissions	None	None	6000+ Tons CO ₂ /yr.	Grid Dependent
Environmental Impact	Low	Low	High	Moderate

7. PUBLICATION BIBLIOGRAPHY

Christoph Kost; Shivenes Shammugam; Verena Fluri; Dominik Peper; Aschkan Davoodi; Thomas Schlegl (2021): Levelized Cost of Electricity: Renewable Energy Technologies (Version 2021).

Encyclopedia Britannica (2018): Keetmanshoop, 7/24/2018. Available online at <https://www.britannica.com/place/Keetmanshoop>.

Ferreres, Maitane (2021): Modelling and Optimization of Combined Solar-Driven Micro Gas Turbine with ORC and Stratified Thermal Energy Storage. Master thesis. Hanze University of Applied Sciences, Groningen, Netherlands.

globalpetrolprices.com (2021): Electricity Prices, 2021.

International Renewable Energy Agency (2017): Electricity storage and renewables: Costs and markets to 2030.

International Renewable Energy Agency (2021): Renewable Power Generation Costs 2020.

Kawamoto, Ryuji; Mochizuki, Hideo; Moriguchi, Yoshihisa; Nakano, Takahiro; Motohashi, Masayuki; Sakai, Yuji; Inaba, Atsushi (2019): Estimation of CO2 Emissions of Internal Combustion Engine Vehicle and Battery Electric Vehicle Using LCA. In *Sustainability* 11 (9), p. 2690. DOI: 10.3390/su11092690.

Mainali, B.; Dhital, R. (2015): Isolated and Mini-Grid Solar PV Systems: An Alternative Solution for Providing Electricity Access in Remote Areas (Case Study from Nepal): Solar Energy Storage.

Odou, Oluwarotimi Delano Thierry; Bhandari, Ramchandra; Adamou, Rabani (2020): Hybrid off-grid renewable power system for sustainable rural electrification in Benin. In *Renewable Energy* 145, pp. 1266–1279. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.06.032.

Solargis (2020): SolarGIS, 2020. Available online at <https://solargis.com/maps-and-gis-data/>.

TheGlobalEconomy.com (2016): Diesel Prices - Country Rankings, 2016. Available online at [TheGlobalEconomy.com](https://www.theglobaleconomy.com), checked on 1/1/2022.

US Agency for International Development (2016): Southern Africa Energy Program. Namibia Country Profile, 2016. Available online at <https://www.usaid.gov/>.

Wikipedia.com (2022a): Antofagasta, 2022. Available online at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Antofagasta>, checked on 1/31/2022.

Wikipedia.com (2022b): Keetmanshoop, 1/2/2022. Available online at <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Keetmanshoop>.